
Exploring an obliterated Jain Temple Site and ‘Stray’ Sculptures from Purulia District of West Bengal

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The archaeological potential of District Purulia is underlined by consistent archaeological discoveries from time to time. Jainism, along with Buddhism and Brahmanism, survived in the different terrains of this region from the later part of the early historic period. However, Jainism appears to have been stronger in profile, as the explored archaeological records suggest. The present survey resulted in the discovery of some new along with hitherto improperly studied sculptural remains from a micro region within the larger area. This study brings forth detailed iconographic features of Jain sculptural remains reported from the site of Anai Jambad. The antiquity of Anai-Jambad has already been studied by some scholars (Mitra 1983: 67-77; Chakrabarti 1993: 128-9; Dutta 2004: 92-93, Chattopadhyay & Acharya 2010: 10-11; Majumder 2017), however, the recent exploration brought to light some new sculptural remains which have not been still reported so far. Among these sculptural remains some are presently displayed in the local museum (Haripada Sahitya Mandir of Purulia) of this district. In the present paper the author has attempted to represent the complete archaeological profile of Anai-Jambad by highlighting the iconoplastic art tradition of the region.

The site encompasses the twin settlements of Anai and Jambad. The former, also the oldest, possess an abandoned Jain religious complex confirmed by the presence of fragmented architectural members and sculptural pieces strewn over the site. A sizable proportion of these specimens have now been shifted to the modern settlement–Jambad. The present site is popularly known as Mahadev-Beda and is situated at a distance of approximately 17km. from Purulia town along the Purulia -Hura road.

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Presently, there is a modern temple constructed by the Sri Sarak Jaina Samiti of Kharkhari, Dhanbad standing over the ruins of the old temple at Anai (**Plate 1**). Inside this temple, six images of Jaina Tīrthānkaras (two each of R̥ṣabhanātha, Candraprabha and Pārśvanātha) are placed on a high cement platform and cemented into the wall (**Plate 2**). According to local villagers, these images were unearthed from the heaps of the ruined temple. As evident, the old temple was affiliated to Jainism which flourished during the early medieval period. During the course of the present exploration, several architectural members which belonged to the old temple were also documented. These include *amlakas*, door jambs, lintels etc. (**Plate 3, 4 & 5**). The Haripada Sahitya Mandir of Purulia town also has some Tīrthānkara images which were discovered from this site. In addition to the Jaina images, some Brahmanical images were also reported from this site. The yield of several Jaina images indicates that this was once a flourishing Jaina site during the early medieval period. Despite currently thriving as a Brahmanical settlement, the site and its Jaina religious ethos are still breathing under the active control/ patronage of the existing Jaina religious community and by their regular worship of the said transferred specimens from the site of Anai. The site also possesses few stray occurrences of Hero stones.

District Purulia including the present study area was one of the most active zones of Jainism during the early medieval period. A series of recent discoveries and extensive field work have helped us to postulate that from the eight-nine century onwards Jainism progressed and reached its zenith in the plateau region of early Bengal (Rāḍha area). The Jaina Nirgrant has lived a comparatively quiet life in the remote, isolated and inaccessible regions of Bengal, of which the Rāḍha provided perhaps the most congenial climate for their existence. Jainism strongly survived in the western and south-western parts of early Bengal (Rāḍha region) up to the thirteenth century CE. This region has a long cultural sequence from the prehistoric times to the early/late medieval period, though its cultural heritage received special momentum (with the radiation of sites, construction activities of temples, installation of icons etc.) with the arrival of political lineages and religious ideologies during the early medieval period. This monumental feature of settlement structure is categorically envisaged by the enormous wealth of archaeological relics in the form of abandoned temple complexes, architectural members and sculptural remains of this region. In all probability, the said database is the best signifier of its early medieval socio-cultural milieu. It is rightly believed that the western sectors of Bengal were devoid of the literate tradition that almost generally characterized the social life of people in the other sub-regions of Bengal in the early medieval period. The general lack of epigraphic material directly associated with Jaina archaeological

remains of western Bengal is probably explained in terms of this lack of tradition. However, a critical study of some lesser known epigraphical and art historical material from the region might throw light on certain hitherto improperly investigated aspects social and political formations in the region.

In the recent past, discoveries of figures of *ācāryas* and monks in the Tīrthaṅkara images from Purulia and Bankura (Majumder 2017:1-6) indicate that in and around these regions Jain monastic system had also developed and Jainism had strongly penetrated the local levels of the society. Discovery of Jain votive stūpas and Jain memorial pillars also indicates the popularity of the Jainism and the involvement of the Jain *ācāryas* and monks towards the expansion of this religious ideology. In absence of epigraphic records, it is very difficult to identify the patrons of these Jain images. However, it is probable to understand from the iconoplastic art of these Jain images that these images were free from the popular royal art style of the then period, i.e. the Pāla - Sena art style.

In the present paper I have attempted to discuss the iconographic details of the six Jain Tīrthaṅkara images from Anai-Jambad (among these six, five images are already reported however, the last one was discovered recently and remains unpublished) and also the other Tīrthaṅkara images which were discovered from this site but are presently displayed in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir museum of Purulia town. The study also highlights the iconoplastic art style of these images and its association with other images.

For the ease of study, I have divided the Jain images of Anai-Jambad into two segments i.e., **A.** Tīrthaṅkara images kept in the modern temple of the village and **B.** Tīrthaṅkara images and other fragmented remains kept in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir, Purulia.

A. Tīrthaṅkara Images kept in the Modern Temple of the Village:

1. Tīrthaṅkara Ṛṣabhanātha:

I have documented two images of Ṛṣabhanātha from Anai-Jambad. Of these two, one is already reported and depicts eight planetary deities on the back-slab (Mitra 1983: 68; Mevissen 2000: 348; Dutta 2004: 93; Majumder 2017). In this image the Jina (**Plate 6**) stands in *kāyotsarga* posture on a double-petalled lotus placed on a *tri-ratha* pedestal. The bull *lāñchana* of the *mūla-nāyaka*, is neatly carved in the centre of the pedestal (the bull occupies the entire central projection) and is placed between two crouching lions (on the adjoining projections). On the left facet of the pedestal is depicted a pair of devotees with their arms joined in adoration, while on the right are votive offerings. The savior is nude; the hair is

dressed in a tall elegant *jaṭājuṭa*. The *keśa-vallarī* of the Jina is falls down the sides of the head and over the shoulders. The Jina is flanked on both sides by stout and partially damaged male *caurī*-bearers. They wear deeply incised loin cloths and elaborate jewellery. Obviously, the modulation of surfaces apparent from the drapery and jewellery are restricted to these *parikara* elements. These *caurī*-bearers stand in *ābhṅga* pose and hold a fly-whisk in their right hands and their left hands are in *kaṭyāvalambita* posture. The back throne of the image consists of posts decorated with mouldings and criss-cross scratched pilasters, supporting a horizontal cross-bar with lightly incised square rhizomes at its ends, above which there are triangular fleurons. On the projected part of the back-slab there are eight planets arranged in a vertical row of four on either side of the Jina. Their depictions are considerably eroded. Those on the right side of the Jina appear to be Sūrya, Maṅgal, Bṛhaspati and Śani; while those on the left side are Soma, Budha, Śukra and Rāhu. All these figures are seated (except Rāhu) and show individual iconographic features. The image measures 67 x 29 x 10 cm.

The second image measures 69 x 32 x 11.5 cm and has not been reported so far. The image is made of chlorite stone (**Plate 7**). The lower portion of rectangular back slab of the Rṣabhanātha image was decorated with two stiff and robust looking *caurī*-bearers, who are the attendants of the *mūla-nāyaka*, with their outer hands in *kaṭyāvalambita* posture and their inner hands holding *cāmaras*, wearing short, almost transparent lower garments and simple ornaments. In the middle portion of the slab were depicted four miniature Tīrthaṅkaras, two on either side of the *mūla-nāyaka*, with their respective *lāñchanas* carved against the double-petalled lotus pedestals. The central portion of the top of the slab is crowned by a triple parasol, flanked on both sides by disembodied hands playing on drums. Two vidyādhara hover in clouds, holding long garlands. The finely carved Jina bears a svelte figure and alucid expression. The *mūla-nāyaka* has elongated ear-lobes and wears an elegant *jaṭājuṭa* with *keśa-vallarī* falling down the sides of the head and over the shoulders. An almost circular *śiraścakra* decorated with intricate patterns of beads and flame tongued border devices adorns the head of the savior. The centre of the *tri-ratha* pedestal has a bull, the *lāñchana* of the *mūla-nāyaka*, placed between two crouching lions with their tails folded and turned upwards. Unfortunately, this image was stolen in the last month of 2023.

2. Tīrthaṅkara Candraprabha:

Two images of Tīrthaṅkara Candraprabha are kept in the modern temple of Anai-Jambad. Of them, one is iconographically very important and it measures 44 cm x 24 cm x

7cm. In this case the Jina is depicted seated in *padmāsana* (Mitra 1983: 68; Dutta 2004: 92; Majumder 2017) with his hands in *dhyāna-mudrā* on a full blown *mahambujapīṭha* having a base comprising of five squat supports on which are carved indistinct objects (**Plate 8**). One of the few seated icons of Tīrthaṅkara so far discovered from Purulia district, the present one was found in damaged condition and subsequently restored. The crescent, i.e. the *lāñchana* of the Jina is depicted on the centre of the lotus seat. The back of the throne is cut roughly along the torso of the central figure and consists of vertical panels topped by horizontal mouldings relieved with short pilasters. On the either side of the Tīrthaṅkara, stand male *caurī*-bearers wearing short lower garments and plain jewellery. The Jina sits under a projected trilinear *catra* slightly damaged at the front. He has elongated ear-lobes and his hair is arranged in schematic curls with as *uṣṇiṣa*. A semi-circular *śiraścakra* gracefully rimmed with rows of leaves and pear like beads surrounds his head. The *prabhāvalī* is generously decorated with floral scrolls and creepers. The *śiraścakra* is flanked on both sides by disembodied hands playing on drums and a vidyādhara holding long garlands and hovering in the clouds.

The second one is a miniature type and it measures 35 cm x 18 cm. This Jaina image (**Plate 9**) is strikingly bare, devoid of embellishments and almost certainly left unfinished (Mitra 1983: 69-70; Dutta 2004: 92; Majumder 2017). The *mūla-nāyaka* stands in *kāyotsarga* posture on a double-petalled lotus seat placed on a *tri-ratha* pedestal under a multi-tiered *chatra*. In the centre of the pedestal the crescent, the *lāñchana* of Candraprabha, is depicted. The Tīrthaṅkara is carved on a recessed portion of the back-slab. He has elongated ears and his hair is arranged in stylized curls with an *uṣṇiṣa*. The back-slab reveals male *caūrī*-bearers, flanking the Jina at the lower corners, and twin vidyādharas at the upper-all four carved on a raised background.

3. Tīrthaṅkara Pārśvanātha:

Among the two images of Tīrthaṅkara Pārśvanātha one is a *pañca-tīrthika* type image (**Plate 10**) and measures 75 cm x 34 cm x 10 cm. The *mūla-nāyaka* stands in *kāyotsarga* on a double-petalled lotus under the usual canopy of a seven-hooded serpent (Mitra 1983: 69; Dutta 2004: 93; Majumder 2017). He wears curly hair with *uṣṇiṣa* and is accompanied on either side by gracefully adorned *caūrī*-bearers. Nāga couple with their tails entwined, the male with arms folded in *namaskāra-mudrā* and the female holding a musical instrument, is shown beside the attendants of the Jina. On the back-slab are carved

four images of Tīrthaṅkaras in *kāyotsarga* two in each side of the *mūla-nāyaka* with their respective *lāñchanas* depicted on a slightly raised pedestal below them. From their cognizance's these Tīrthaṅkaras can be identified as Vāsupūjya and Padmaprabha to the right of the *mūla-nāyaka*, and Neminātha and Mahāvīra to his left. The upper part of the stele contains the usual vidyādhara couple, the *prātihāryas* of heavenly hands playing on musical instruments and a projected three-tiered *catra* surmounting the snake hoods. The face and the torso of the Jina are slightly abraded. The *tri-ratha* pedestal reveals crouching lions, a female devotee and offerings.

The remaining one is the *caubisi* type of image (Mitra 1983: 68-9; Dutta 2004: 93; Majumder 2017) and among all these images the present one is largest (136 x 65 x 12 cm.) and the most graceful sculpture among the group. The Jina (**Plate 11**) stands in *kāyotsarga* under a seven-hooded snake, which is surmounted by a tri-linear *chatra*. Nāga couple with their hands folded and tails inter-coiled springs gracefully and rhythmically from the central protection of a *tri-ratha* pedestal to just beside the feet of the savior. A pair of kneeling devotees with their hands joined in *añjali-mudrā* is seen on the plane of the pedestal, which bears the representation of crouching lions on the remaining facets. The Jina is flanked by two male *caūri*-bearers standing in graceful *ābhaṅga* pose wearing lower garments and bedecked with jewellery. On the edge of the rectangular back-slab are the twenty four Tīrthaṅkaras arranged in pairs, one above the other. The *lāñchanas* of the Jinās are carved on their pedestals and quite a number of them are recognizable. Flying vidyādhara couple holding garlands is seen high up on the back-slab.

B. Tīrthaṅkara Images and other fragments kept in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir, Purulia:

1. Tīrthaṅkara Ṛṣabhanātha:

A *Pañca-tīrthika* type of Tīrthaṅkara Ṛṣabhanātha image (**Plate 12**) discovered from the present site is presently displayed in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir, Purulia. The museum specimen, which is partially damaged (head of the image is missing), measures 84 x 40 x 20cm and iconographically is very similar to the Ṛṣabhanātha image from the same site. The image has an elongated *prabhā* which is embellished with beaded and flame-tongued border devices and has a flowering twig on the either side. The image is carved out of quartzite schist. Two partially damaged vidyādharas holding long garlands are depicted on the extreme top most corners of the rectangular back slab. The depictions of the clouds are

noteworthy. The representation of the heavenly hands playing a drum is present. The *mūla-nāyaka* is flanked by two male *caurī*-bearers standing in *ābhṅga* posture and their left hands are in *kaṭyāvalambita* posture and the right hands hold the fly-whisk. The back throne of the image consists of posts decorated with mouldings and criss-cross scratched pilasters, supporting a horizontal cross-bar with lightly incised square rhizomes at its ends, above which there are triangular fleurons. On the projected part of the back-slab are depicted four miniature Jinas standing in *kāyotsarga* posture on double-petalled pedestals, two on either side of the *mūla-nāyaka*. Due to regular worship, the iconographic details of the image are not well delineated. Interestingly, tiny figures of two devotees is depicted, in *namaskāra-mudrā* (folded hands), on the left side of the *caurī*-bearer just above the *pañca-ratha* pedestal. The bull is flanked by two crouching lions facing opposite directions on either end of the pedestal and the remaining portion is left blank.

2. Tīrthaṅkara Śāntinātha:

A beautiful image of Tīrthaṅkara Śāntinātha (80 x 40 x 15 cm) is also display in the said museum that was discovered from the present study area. The Jina (**Plate 13**) is in *kāyotsarga* and *samapādasthānaka* postures and stands on a full blown lotus placed on a *sapta-ratha* pedestal. The arms of the Jina hang down vertically along the slender torso and the finger tips touch the thigh on either side. The *sapta-ratha* pedestal of the image is very simple and the central *ratha* is adorned with the *lāñchana* of the Tīrthaṅkara i.e., deer, which is flanked by two crouching lions, facing opposite directions. The remaining *rathas* of the pedestal are completely blank. A very simple almost oval *śiraścakra* adorns the head of the savior. Above the *śiraścakra* and just below the top border of the back slab is a centrally placed tri-linear *catra* flanked by a drum and a pair of cymbals struck by disembodied hands. Two vidyādhara or garland-bearers are depicted on both corner sides at the top of the back-slab. The *mūla-nāyaka* is flanked by two male *caurī*-bearers standing in *ābhṅga* posture and their left hands are in *kaṭyāvalambita* posture and the right hands hold the fly-whisk. Both of them are highly bejeweled and have a small halo behind their heads.

On the edge of the back-slab are eight planets arranged in a vertical row of four on either side of the Jina. Those on the dexter side appear to be Sūrya, Maṅgal, Bṛhaspati and Śani; while those on the left side are Soma, Budha, Śukra and Rāhu. All these planetary deities are seated in usual posture on double-petalled lotus and holding their respective attributes. The back of the throne consists of jeweled posts supporting a cross-bar on which are triangular foliated plaques.

In addition to the above mentioned two Tīrthaṅkara images, there are some other fragmented sculptural remains associated with Jainism that had been collected from the various locality of the present site and are currently on display in the museum. The details of these specimens are given below:

Sl. No.	Details of the Fragmented Sculptural Remains	Measurements
1.	A broken palm of a sculpture, probably the part of the main deity.	11.5 x 5 cm
2.	Fragmented part of a back-slab of a Jaina image, depicting a small miniature Tīrthaṅkara probably Ṛṣabhanātha due to the elegant <i>jaṭājuta</i> over head.	10.5 x 6 cm
3.	Torso of a Jaina Tīrthaṅkara collected from the ruins of the temple at Anai-Jambad.	10.4 x 4.5 cm.
4.	Torso of a Jaina Tīrthaṅkara having hair arranged in small curls.	7.5 x 4 cm
5.	Torso of a Jaina Tīrthaṅkara	7.2 x 4.3 cm
6.	Torso of a Jaina Tīrthaṅkara. Both the hands of the Jina are also damaged	8 x 4.5 cm
7.	A torso of an attendant of Jaina Tīrthaṅkara, holding a <i>cauri</i> in his right hand.	12 x 7 cm
8.	A three tiered umbrella depicting lotus petals. This was found from the ruins of the temple.	6 x 11 cm
9.	Torso of a <i>caurī</i> -bearer of a Jaina Tīrthaṅkara. The <i>caurī</i> -bearer wears a <i>dhoti</i> and other ornaments. This figure was detached from the main image.	13 x 7 cm
10.	A five-linear decorated parasol most probably part of a Jaina image.	13 x 5 cm
11.	A middle portion of a male image. Most probably part of an attendant of Tīrthaṅkara images.	10 x 5.6 cm
12.	A flying figure of an image holding garland in his right hand.	15 x 8 cm

Observation:

In the foregoing pages I have analyzed the explored data to attain a comprehensible picture of an archaeological site and their sculptural remains. It is quite clear from the above data that these evidences, ascribable to the Jaina pantheon, are well connected with the growth of Jainism and the spread of Jaina settlements, rituals and their relationship with the sculptural art of the said region. It is quite obvious that such concentration of Jaina heritage is not restricted to this particular site. The site has extended connection with the other Jaina site in the Rāḍha region of early Bengal.

It is also worth mentioning here that though the Jaina sculptural heritage of the present site was discussed by some scholars earlier, however, they failed to provide the complete picture about the sculptural wealth of this site. In the present paper I have summarized all the Jaina sculptural remains which are at present displayed in the site itself as well as the Jaina sculptural and architectural remains housed in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir museum of Purulia district. It shows that the present site Anai-Jambad was one of the important Jaina centers in this region during the early medieval times. Sculptural and the architectural remains like door-jams, *amlaka*, *kalasa* and others found from the site point towards the existence of temple/affiliated to Jainism but after the gradual decline of Jainism these were abandoned and slowly collapsed. As a result of this, now we can get only the Jaina images from the present site and scholars generally mistake to reconstruct the actual context of these Jaina images. Though these six Jaina Tīrthaṅkara images are at present placed in a modern temple and the present Jaina community regularly worships them, however, these images are a strong example to prove that the present site was a flourishing Jaina center during 9th to 13th century CE and probably served as one of the important pilgrimage center of Jainism in that time.

The Jaina sculptures elaborately described and discussed above on stylistic and iconographic grounds may be assigned to the period between the 9th - 10th to 12th centuries CE (except the small image of Tīrthaṅkara Candraprabha (**Plate 9**), which probably belong to the late medieval period). Among them, the *caubisi* type of Pārśvanātha image is largest one and most probably this image was the object of principal worship in the temple of Anai-Jambad. P.M. Mitra in his paper (1983: 70) mentioned that this Pārśvanātha image was ‘most finished and accomplished example’ among the five images from this site. However, it is worth mentioning here that the pedestal of the present image is not comparatively decorated like the other Pārśvanātha images in this district specially the Pārśvanātha images from Pakbirra and

Suisa (Majumder 2017). The representation of a nāga couple with their tails inter-coiled is gracefully depicted in most of the Pārśvanātha images from the Rāḍha region, however, in the present image very miniature figures of nāga couple, with a snake canopy over their heads, is depicted and their inter-coiled not elegantly presented. Overall the figure of the *mūla-nāyaka* is also bulky in nature. Though the nāga canopy of the image and the coils of the snake are stylishly executed this type of representation is not commonly found in the Rāḍha region.

All the Jaina Tīrthaṅkara images which are discussed here in general do not exhibit the work of high quality of craftsmanship except the Śāntinātha image which is presently displayed in the Haripada Sahitya Mandir museum of Purulia. In most of the images the pedestal is not elaborately decorated only the cognizance of the Jina is placed at the center of the pedestal. The body proportions of the *mūla-nāyaka* are not perfectly maintained when compared with other Jaina images of this district. The back-slab and the *caurī*-bearers are not highly ornamented. The smallest image in the collection i.e. the image of Tīrthaṅkara Candraprabha shows that Jainism was survived in the present study area upto the 15th century CE. This was a portable image and most probably worshipped in a house of a devotee of Jain ideology.

The Jaina sculptural remains found from different parts of this district as well as other parts of the Rāḍha region of Bengal were products created by the fusion of the art idioms of neighboring areas of the Chhotanagpur plateau region and were laid in an essentially local matrix from which came out this distinct school of a regional tradition. The present sculptural remains exhibit that among this regional art tradition there are some micro level variations. As a result of these micro level art traditions, the distinct centre of art in the Rāḍha region strengthen its popularity over the so called classical tradition art style in the other parts of eastern Indian is concerned. The regional traditions were guided by powerful local ateliers which were not driven necessarily by the ideas of the plastic art exhibited in the mainstream 'Pāla-Sena' idiom of expression. The modeling appears to be softened by the artists in a way that result into, in the sculptural productions of the Rāḍha region, great strength and vigor.

The work thus shows, in the form of a case study, that firstly among the western sectors of West Bengal there are some variations from area to area which deserve more careful archaeological investigation in order to understand the nature and pattern of distribution of early medieval sites and for locating the regional artistic as well as stylistic identities; secondly, it indicates that such micro-regional case studies are expected to throw new light on the nature of the art styles which were evolved during the early medieval period in the

Chhotanagpur plateau region with involvement of the local tradition and also represent a complete picture about an archaeological site during the early medieval period.

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Bibliography:

Chakrabarti, Dilip K. (1993). *Archaeology of Eastern India: Chhotanagpur Plateau and West Bengal*. New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal.

Chattopadhyay, R.K. and D. Acharya, (2010). 'Contexts of Early Mediaeval Remains of Purulia: Researching Ideologies', *Pratnatattv*, volume 16: 9-31.

Dutta, Debajani Mitra. (2004). *A Survey of Jainism and Jaina Art of Eastern India, With Special Emphasis on Bengal from the Earliest Period to the Thirteenth Century A.D.* Kolkata: R.N. Bhattacharya.

Majumder, Shubha. (2017). '*Jaina Remains of Ancient Bengal: A Study in Archaeology, Art and Iconography*', unpublished PhD thesis submitted to the University of Calcutta.

_____. (2017). 'A Rare Icon of Tīrthaṅkara Mallinātha from Purulia, West Bengal: An Analytic Approach', *Pratnatattv*, volume 23: 1-6.

Mevisen, Gerd J.R. (2000). 'Corpus of Jaina Stone Sculptures Bearing *graha*'s as Subsidiary Figures', *Berliner Indologische Studien* (Reinbek), volume 13/14: 343-400.

Mitra, Pratip Kumar. (1983). 'Jaina Sculptures From Anai-Jambad'. *Jaina Journal*, volume 18/2 (October): 67-72.